

Professional Burnout in Contemporary Health Systems Through the Lens of Electronic Health

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ABSTRACT

Burnout has sparked global interest, as numerous researchers have been involved in national studies regarding its symptoms. It is described as a form of prolonged, chronic, occupational stress that exceeds the limits of endurance or the individual's ability to cope with it. Its appearance is multifactorial and is directly related to the place and object of work and to demographic and other characteristics of the individual. People who experience professional burnout experience emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and reduced personal fulfillment, all of which have an increased risk of medical errors. At the same time, the development of e-health has transformed health systems. While these new digital tools have been created to increase the efficiency, quality and safety of care, research has shown that misuse and overwork can exacerbate burnout. This article deals with the relationship between burnout and medical errors through the prism of e-health. Studying articles from the international literature, he analyzes the different theoretical models of burnout, analyzes the human factor in medical errors and evaluates the impact of digital health technologies. It focuses on the design of human-based health technologies to carry out the proper implementation of modern health systems in order to reduce burnout and patient safety. At the same time, it points out the importance of the well-being of health professionals as a determining factor in the quality of healthcare. Supportively, the happier the health workforce, the greater the safety of patients and the more the efficiency of the health system increases.

KEYWORDS: Professional burnout; Healthcare professionals; Patient safety; Medical errors; e-Health

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1. INTRODUCTION

In a workplace with a stressful environment, characterized by complexity, multi-layered structure, diverse professional teams that interdepend and interact, healthcare professionals are called upon to work together in order to provide comprehensive patient care. Developments in the medical sector are important, but new concerns arise that are related to both patients and health care workers, who are looking for solutions. There is a growing perception in the research field that work is a source of stress. Unlike stress that comes from personal life or the wider environment, dealing with work stress cannot be easily achieved, since the employee cannot change his work role or the conditions prevailing in his work environment on his own. Prolonged stress at work is likely

to make individuals feel exhausted and unable to cope. It can also cause physical and mental symptoms, create health problems and changes in behavior. The major challenges that the healthcare sector is experiencing threaten the survival of many hospitals, and it is a difficult time for workers in this sector. Although many countries are struggling to meet these challenges, the continued evolution of healthcare models does not lead to better outcomes, as shown by rising levels of burnout among healthcare professionals, or safer care, as shown by the increasing number of medical errors^[1-3].

Healthcare professionals are expected to provide the same quality of care with fewer resources, while patients' expectations for care increase fueling feelings of exhaustion

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and depersonalization of the healthcare provider, a situation that leads to poor communication with patients, creating a vicious circle. Research on burnout among health workers is constantly increasing, in terms of its causes, indications, appearance, development, consequences, as well as its prevention and treatment. Healthcare professionals are very likely to develop the syndrome due to a number of factors, mainly due to the great responsibility that stems from the particular nature of the health professions. Working in healthcare and care facilities is characterized by tension and daily contact with people in vulnerable emotional situations, resulting in greater risks of stress and burnout for employees and requiring greater energy consumption. Also, burnout in health workers may mean much more than in any other profession because of its consequences. A more critical aspect of the issue is its correlation with the quality of care and care services provided^[2,4].

Patient safety, although one aspect of the quality of healthcare services provided, is nevertheless a key component of a quality health system, which is significantly hampered by medical errors. Medical errors can be attributed to the medical and other staff, the health system but also to the interaction of the two factors and at the same time to the relationships between health professionals and the patient. They pose a threat to the safety of patients, have serious negative mental, moral and material consequences for patients who have suffered them during their hospitalization, while equally important are the consequences for the individual doctor, the employees, the health care system and, by extension, the economy and society as a whole. A crucial point of the issue is the relationship between burnout syndrome and the performance of an incorrect medical act or omission as well as the consequences of the syndrome on the quality of health care and care provided^[5-7].

2. METHODS

2.1. Purpose of the study

The purpose of this article is to study the relationship between eHealth in Healthcare Burnout and patient safety. In particular, the possibilities and limitations of digital health that have an impact on patient safety are examined. The greater the burnout in the health system, the more medical errors increase and patient safety decreases. Also, e-health has two sides, whether it acts as a protective mechanism that enhances patient safety, or acts as an aggravating factor that intensifies the stress of health workers. Through the literature analysis, the need for a human-centered, strategic use of e-health in modern health systems is highlighted. This study seeks to elucidate the interactions between burnout, patient safety, and digital health tools. It also focuses on the organizational and technological conditions by which eHealth can empower healthcare professionals rather than undermine their well-being^[8,9].

2.2. Material and analysis

To conduct this systematic review, the researchers followed the protocol Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA). The researchers followed a five-stage process: identifying relevant studies, selecting studies, mapping data, synthesizing, and presenting results. Electronic databases and digital libraries were used in the literature review, between January 2020 and December 2025, such as: PubMed, Scopus, Medline, Web of Science, Google Scholar, PsycINFO, CINAHL, EBSCO and Elsevier ScienceDirect. The search strategy used keywords: burnout, healthcare professionals, patient safety, medical errors, e-health, electronic health records, clinical decision support systems, digital health, and artificial intelligence. Selection criteria included relevance to research objectives, publication in peer-reviewed journals, and contribution to a theoretical, empirical, or conceptual understanding of the relationship between burnout, patient safety, and digital health technologies. Both quantitative and qualitative studies, systematic reviews, and conceptual work were examined.

Figure 1. PRISMA Flow diagram of the systematic review.

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The information specialist in the study team exported the results to Zotero and removed duplicates, retaining 561 articles. Following a preliminary assessment, two researchers reviewed the titles and abstracts to assess their relevance to the study's objectives, focusing on those with broadly applicable insights. This process led to the retention of 126 articles, with 435 being retrieved. The same reviewers then conducted a thorough evaluation of the full texts of the selected articles, making decisions based on their alignment with the study's goals. Ultimately, 38 articles were excluded after this detailed review, leaving 44 articles for inclusion in the qualitative synthesis. A PRISMA flow diagram (Figure 1) is provided to illustrate the professional burnout characteristics from surveys through the development of Electronic Health.

3. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK OF PROFESSIONAL BURNOUT

The concept of professional burnout has received increased attention worldwide, as the incidence of its symptoms has been documented in numerous national and international studies. It is described as a form of prolonged, chronic occupational stress that exceeds an individual's resilience or ability to cope. A large number of factors can contribute to its onset, mainly related to the work environment, the nature of the work, as well as demographic and other individual characteristics. Due to its recognized and significant impact on individuals and organizations, burnout has been extensively studied across the social sciences, management and organizational sciences, and management practice^[10-14].

3.1. Historical and theoretical framework of professional burnout

Internationally, professional exhaustion is called burnout. Etymologically, the term describes progressive internal exhaustion to the point of burnout^[6]. The concept of professional burnout began to develop systematically in the 1960s. The first person to study it as a psychological syndrome was Herbert J. Freudenberger in the United States, who, through observations of staff at a clinic for young people with addiction problems, recorded the occurrence of a series of psychosomatic disorders. He found that individuals who developed professional burnout exhibited gradual emotional exhaustion, loss of motivation, and reduced professional commitment^[15].

According to Freudenberger, burnout is a state of fatigue or exhaustion resulting from intense dedication to a cause, lifestyle, or relationship that fails to provide the expected rewards. The syndrome is directly linked to the individual's commitment to their work and to the frustration arising from not achieving their goals. Factors such as a lack of variety and inadequate feedback in the workplace contribute significantly to the onset and development of burnout^[15]. Christina Maslach made a decisive contribution by defining burnout as a multidimensional syndrome that develops in the workplace and is characterized by three basic dimensions:

emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and reduced sense of personal accomplishment^[16,17]. The contribution of industrial psychology was also significant, approaching burnout as a form of work-related stress directly linked to job satisfaction, feelings of frustration, commitment, and dissatisfaction with work relationships, as well as with the general characteristics of the work environment^[11,13]. The importance of the phenomenon was officially recognized by the World Health Organization, which included burnout in the International Classification of Diseases (ICD-11) as an occupational syndrome related to chronic work stress^[18].

3.2. Theoretical approaches and interpretative models of burnout

In their attempt to interpret the syndrome of professional burnout, researchers have developed a series of theoretical approaches aimed at identifying the factors that can contribute to both the onset and progression of burnout, as well as its effects on individuals, the workplace, and, by extension, the social environment^[12,16]. The most prevalent theoretical framework is Maslach's three-dimensional model, which describes burnout through three distinct dimensions, each accompanied by different symptoms^[19,20]. Emotional exhaustion, considered the most critical dimension, expresses the state in which the employee experiences intense physical and emotional fatigue, loss of motivation, and lack of energy, resulting in a generalized feeling of disappointment in relation to professional expectations^[13]. Depersonalization, as the second dimension of professional burnout, often functions as a necessary defense mechanism for the employee, allowing emotional distancing from work demands. At this stage, the employee becomes alienated, develops superficial, cynical relationships, treats patients with a dismissive attitude, and behaves accordingly, expressing generalized detachment. The lack of personal accomplishment constitutes the third dimension of burnout and reflects a condition in which the employee experiences diminished personal success, ineffectiveness, and negative self-evaluation, resulting in reduced productivity.

In general, individuals feel unable to achieve their goals or fulfil their expectations, experience disappointment, consider themselves inadequate, and often attribute achievements to luck, while developing a broader sense of lack of control over their lives^[19,20]. Alternative theoretical approaches include the gradual model of Edelwich and Brodsky, which views burnout as an evolutionary process consisting of four stages: initial enthusiasm, stagnation, frustration and apathy, culminating in disengagement from professional task^[21]. Similarly, Cherniss' interactive model emphasizes the dynamic interaction between the individual and the work environment, highlighting organizational factors such as excessive demands, lack of support, limited control, and role ambiguity as central contributors to burnout^[8].

3.3. Psychometric assessment of professional burnout

Based on theoretical models, researchers have created tools to measure burnout, aiming at the systematic study and recording of it "from theory to practice", in order to provide information, first to understand it as a situation and then to deal with it^[22]. Some of them are more widespread and widely accepted by researchers, because they are considered easier to use-apply and at the same time effective. The three-dimensional model of Maslach and Jackson is one of the most important models, which projects three dimensions of burnout, with different symptoms in each dimension. "Emotional exhaustion", which is perhaps the most critical dimension, expresses the situation in which the employee is in a physical and emotional exhaustion, loss of mood, lack of energy, i.e. experiencing a general disappointment in his expectations. "Depersonalization", as the second dimension of burnout, is a necessary defense mechanism for the employee, in an effort to protect himself and get rid of the burden he feels. The worker begins to distance himself, to become alienated, to develop superficial and cynical relationships, to treat patients with disparagement and to treat them accordingly, manifesting a denial of everything. The "lack of personal achievement" is the third dimension, which expresses the situation in which the employee acquires a sense of reduced personal success, feels ineffective and evaluates himself negatively, as a result of which he is no longer productive. In general, he feels that he is not able to achieve his goals or realize his desires and expectations, he experiences a general disappointment, he thinks that he is particularly inadequate, he is not happy with his achievements, he believes that they are due to luck, having a general feeling that he cannot control his life^[20].

The Maslach Burnout Inventory is the most widely accepted standard for assessing the syndrome. This tool measures the three dimensions of burnout, asking the employee to answer twenty-two questions, using the seven-point Likert scale, where 0 represents "never" and 6 represents "every day"^[10]. "Emotional burnout" is the key element of MBI, since the depletion of emotional reserves is the main element of burnout. The second subscale, "depersonalization", evaluates the individual's behavior towards the patient/client. It describes any negative behavior, such as distrust of people, dissatisfaction, and frustration at work. It was later renamed "cynicism". The subscale of "reduced personal achievement" captures the individual's sense of reduced efficiency or performance in relation to what he expects^[23].

In order to fill any gaps in this first tool, the new "Maslach Burnout Inventory- General Survey" scale was created, which examines burnout in all occupations, since the Maslach model is more related to staff in the provision of social services, but also in education. The Burnout Measure measurement tool identifies burnout with one dimension and evaluates it with a single scale, corresponding to the emotional exhaustion of the MBI, which gives an overall

score. It is considered reliable and departs from the philosophy of other models^[24]. In the Cherniss interactive model, burnout is described as a process that develops in three phases. The first, "work stress", is caused by the disruption of the relationship between the necessary and available resources to enable the individual to complete personal goals and the demands of the work environment in an appropriate way. The employee then passes to "exhaustion", which is expressed in mental fatigue, fatigue, distance from the public and lack of interest in his future professional career. The professional field is a source of exhaustion for the employee, as although he tried to achieve everything he aimed for, he finds that his requests are not accepted by the employer or colleagues and that he will have to work hard to do what is taken for granted. He feels a constant strain that if he does not deal with it properly, he can gradually lead to abstention, to resignation. This is followed by the "defensive ending" where he shows significant behavioral changes in order to protect himself from prolonged psychological pressure. It is expressed with negative emotions, anger, denial, cynicism and indifference towards others, psychological transitions and conflicts. It is presented as the last attempt of the employee to manage to stay in his job^[25].

In the model of Edelwich and Brodsky, burnout is defined as a process that develops in four stages, one after the other during the course of the professional career. The individual begins his career with "enthusiasm", aims high, and there are many times when he has unattainable goals. Work plays a central role in his life, in which he spends his time and invests most of his energy. He also invests excessively in all the relationships he develops with patients, trying to derive every possible satisfaction. However, he becomes frustrated when he realizes that his work is ultimately not in line with what he expected. Thus, he enters "doubt and inertia". The person continues to work, but realizes that while he devotes himself more to his work, he does not receive the expected results and his needs are not met through it. The enthusiasm he felt is replaced by disappointment. Long working hours, lack of free time and minimal social contacts become particularly important. Thus, day by day, he loses the motivation to work and gradually demystifies it. This is followed by "disappointment and frustration" where the person becomes discouraged and frustrated when he realizes that the efforts he made to achieve through his work were in vain. In order to be able to deal with what he feels, he will revise his expectations or leave his job, the source of stress. The final stage for the worker is "apathy", where he now functions mechanically, without expectations and dreams, keeps away from responsibilities, works to ensure his survival, without investing in his work^[26].

The Copenhagen model is a newer model, designed to correct the shortcomings of the Maslach rating standard. Based on this model, Kristensen and colleagues developed the Copenhagen Burnout Inventory questionnaire, which

examines burnout in workers and in other professions and not only in humanities^[27]. Another accepted standard for assessing burnout, mainly used in health workers, is the Staff Burnout Scale^[28], which contains elements related to behavior and physiology and is structured according to the Maslach scale. It evaluates negative behaviors, psychological, emotional, sociological, that cause the burnout syndrome. Finally, the used Oldenburg Burnout Inventory scale was made for the purpose of two-sided expression of questions, so that it is structured as half negative and half positive, allowing multifaceted coverage of the building blocks of burnout^[12].

4. PROFESSIONAL BURNOUT AS A CONTRIBUTING FACTOR TO MEDICAL ERRORS

The professional burnout of healthcare professionals has been recognized in international literature as one of the most important human factors contributing to medical errors. Emotional and physical exhaustion, a key dimension of burnout syndrome, reduces concentration, impairs memory, and slows clinical decision-making. In high-pressure environments, such as hospitals, these effects make healthcare professionals more vulnerable to errors in diagnosis, treatment, and medication^[29,30]. At the same time, depersonalization, which is characterized by emotional detachment and a cynical attitude towards patients, can undermine the quality of communication and care. Reduced empathy and poor communication increase the likelihood of misunderstandings, incomplete information, and incorrect clinical procedures, all of which are directly linked to medical errors. In addition, a reduced sense of personal achievement can lead to lower professional commitment and reduced attention to detail, which are critical to patient safety^[1,31].

Research data indicate that professional burnout is associated with an increased risk of future serious medical errors, as perceived by healthcare professionals. When professionals are not in good mental and physical health, the performance of healthcare systems deteriorates, affecting the quality of care provided and patient safety. Therefore, professional burnout is not only an individual welfare problem, but also a critical issue of healthcare safety and quality, which requires interventions at both the individual and organizational levels^[32].

5. MEDICAL ERRORS AND PATIENT SAFETY

‘Medical errors’ and ‘adverse events’ or ‘unwanted events’ in patient care have been found to occur with particularly high frequency at the international level, both in public and private healthcare, posing a serious threat to patient safety^[30,33]. Medical errors can be attributed to medical and other healthcare personnel, the healthcare system itself, and their interaction. Given that the phenomenon is not easy to address, as the causes are not superficial and require in-depth investigation, it is necessary to place particular

emphasis on prevention, the identification of risk factors that contribute to medical errors and adverse events, as well as their elimination or, at least, their substantial reduction^[34,35]. The significance of this phenomenon has become particularly apparent in recent years, as medical errors are among the leading causes of preventable harm and mortality worldwide, making it imperative to prevent them systematically and deal with them in an organized manner^[36].

5.1. Typology and classification of medical errors

In the international literature we do not find a universally accepted classification of medical errors. We find that there are many ways to categorize them, as they include a wide range of events. Based on the stage of the therapeutic process, are divided into errors^[37]:

- treatment, such as errors or omissions during a treatment procedure or surgery, errors in the method or administration of medication, misinterpretation in the prescription, inappropriate treatment, delay in starting treatment
- diagnosis, such as incorrect or inadequate or delayed diagnosis, inability to use appropriate diagnostic tools or diagnostic test results, use of outdated methods
- prevention, such as skipping repeat checks
- other factors, such as errors in the use of medical equipment (e.g. damage to medical equipment), communication difficulties, risk of nosocomial infections, etc.

Diagnostic errors are the most common and frequent errors, mainly in pathology and emergency medicine and although they are more likely to be prevented, they are also more likely to cause harm^[38]. An additional categorization tries to express the level of severity of possible damage, which ranges from cases that can cause medical error to permanent disability or death of a patient^[37].

5.2. Human and organizational risk factors

The occurrence of medical errors is related to a variety of factors, which can be divided into human and organizational aspects. Among the most important human factors are fatigue, understaffing, long working hours, and inadequate training. In the health sector in particular, professional burnout has been recognized as a critical factor that significantly increases the risk of medical errors^[30,32]. At the same time, organizational factors, such as the lack of clearly defined procedures, inadequate communication between healthcare team members, and the absence of a well-developed safety culture, contribute significantly to conditions that favour error occurrence. In this light, medical errors should be treated as the result of systemic weaknesses rather than as the consequence of individual fault^[34,39]. The consequences of medical errors are dire and affect multiple levels. For patients, errors can lead to a deterioration in their health, prolonged hospitalization, permanent disabilities, or even loss of life. At the same time, patients’ families

experience intense psychological stress and a loss of trust in the healthcare system^[30].

Healthcare professionals involved in medical errors often experience intense anxiety, feelings of guilt, and professional insecurity, a phenomenon described in the international literature as the “second victim”. At the organizational level, medical errors entail increased financial costs, legal implications, and an overall deterioration in the quality of healthcare services provided^[40,41].

6. STRATEGIES FOR THE PREVENTION AND SYSTEMATIC MANAGEMENT OF MEDICAL ERRORS

Several intervention strategies have been proposed, some focus on preventing burnout, while others try to treat it after it manifests itself^[23]. Also, they can be person-centered, directed by the organism, or combined directed by the human and the organism. Treatment aimed at shifting from burnout treatment to preventive health and well-being of health professionals, as well as assessing factors that will increase job satisfaction and promote a balanced lifestyle, is an effective solution to reduce the risk of burnout^[42]. In health professionals, there is a negative relationship between job satisfaction and burnout. It is a controversial issue whether burnout results in employees feeling dissatisfied or whether the loss of job satisfaction precedes and manufactures burnout^[43].

Most healthcare organizations operate in the context that both are solely the responsibility of the individual physician, with the result that organizations often seek solutions that will not lead to substantial improvement, such as stress management laboratories. These strategies are viewed with skepticism by doctors as a disingenuous attempt by the organization to deal with the problem. Also, by presenting the issue as an individual problem, setting aside organizational factors, individual doctors may be led to seek solutions that are beneficial to themselves, but detrimental to the organization and, by extension, to society, such as the reduction of professional effort^[44]. Southwick and Charney, record ten psychological and social factors associated with stronger resilience: coping with fear, moral compass, faith, use of social support, good role models, good physical condition, stimuli, cognitive and emotional flexibility, meaning, purpose and growth in life, realistic optimism^[45].

Doctors often ask about what can be done to reduce stress levels and eliminate burnout. Drummond observes how this question assumes that burnout is a problem that has a solution. According to the researcher, burnout has no solution, because it is not a problem in the first place. There is no simple solution to apply it so that the problem disappears in one go. So, as they cannot find "what" with which to solve the problem, they return to their old work habits and leave the possibility of changing things. In fact, burnout is a dilemma, and dilemmas are incessant balancing acts that require unstoppable action.

7. PROFESSIONAL BURNOUT AND MEDICAL ERROR AS A THREAT TO PATIENT SAFETY

In recent years, enhancing patient safety from errors and adverse events has become a key objective of health policies, especially those focused on improving the quality of healthcare. Patient safety, although one aspect of the quality of healthcare services provided, is nevertheless a key component of a quality healthcare system, which is significantly hampered by medical errors^[46,47]. Errors and adverse events in patient care are observed with great frequency internationally, both in public and private healthcare, and have become, in a sense, a “common” phenomenon. It is true that in hospitals we face the following dilemma: on the one hand, the use of technology can undoubtedly “save lives”; on the other hand, there is a risk of errors^[48,49]. Medical errors often cause adverse events, but this does not mean that all adverse events are due to medical error. Indeed, the majority are estimated to be the result of iatrogenic mistakes, which sometimes cause harm and sometimes create dangerous situations for patients without ultimately causing any harm^[50]. Undoubtedly, they constitute adverse events during patient treatment and care. As is well known, developments and recent advances in the medical field are essential, but new concerns have arisen for patients and health professionals seeking solutions. The stress and negative thoughts caused by the unpleasant feeling of fear of loss of life and illness, the difficulties of the working environment, the inadequate training of medical and nursing staff, make it difficult to interact with patients, while also putting emotional pressure on employees, leading to tension, lack of job satisfaction and other serious consequences, the most common of which is the mental illness of depression^[32].

To the above, we must add that there is a perception in the research field that work is increasingly a source of stress^[51]. Work, like family, is one of two areas from which adults derive satisfaction in life. They are also a common source of stressful experiences. Unlike stress that comes from personal life or the wider environment, dealing with work stress is not easy, as employees cannot change the conditions that prevail in the workplace on their own^[52]. As we have noted, work-related stress can leave individuals feeling exhausted and unable to cope. It can also cause physical and mental symptoms, create health problems, and lead to changes in behavior^[53]. To combat professional burnout, it is necessary to change working conditions and manage conflicts in the workplace^[54], since most studies conducted in our country emphasize the negative relationship between job satisfaction and professional burnout^[55,56]. Furthermore, research from many studies indicates that burnout, fatigue, stress, and diminished well-being among healthcare professionals negatively impact the performance of healthcare systems. When doctors are not at their best, the efficiency of healthcare systems may suffer^[57].

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The positive opposite of professional burnout is commitment, characterized by vigor and dedication to work. Having a committed medical workforce is critical for healthcare organizations to achieve their institutional goals and mission. Furthermore, the well-being of doctors, beyond benefiting individual doctors, is directly linked to the provision of high-quality patient care. It is also related to that of other members of the healthcare team^[58], as well as the long-term sustainability of the organization and is also an indicator of quality^[8,59]. Since patient safety is linked to the health of staff in healthcare organizations, in an effort to improve patient safety, but also the safety of doctors themselves, well-designed interventions are needed to prevent burnout and to identify and treat distress in doctors, as well as changes in their training programs^[32].

In summary, medical errors are often attributable to “problematic systems” that lead to mistakes or failures to prevent them. Therefore, to avoid medical errors and adverse events, healthcare systems must be organized and operated safely at all levels^[60]. To organize safe healthcare, a significant challenge for leadership is the creation of conditions that foster the development of professional satisfaction^[61]. Health professionals and policy makers agree that the provision of high-quality health services depends on the ability of health personnel to work together as a team, so that the search for “mutually acceptable” ways for management to resolve conflicts can help to smooth them over, ensure consistency of services, avoid disputes, and maintain a climate of good cooperation^[62].

Given the strong link between staff commitment to patient safety and organizational outcomes, organizational management has a significant business opportunity to invest in efforts to promote commitment and reduce burnout^[8]. The participatory management model is referred to as the transition to high-quality services. It focuses on upgrading the most important factor, the human resources themselves, while placing people at the center of actions^[62]. Furthermore, organizational management should evaluate not only quality and financial performance factors, such as patient numbers and patient satisfaction, but also other factors, including organizational culture and leadership. Still, it should also select and assess, at regular intervals, various dimensions of staff well-being, such as satisfaction/fulfilment, professional burnout, commitment, fatigue, stress, emotional health, and dimensions of well-being/quality of life^[8].

8. THE ROLE OF E-HEALTH IN PROFESSIONAL BURNOUT AND PATIENT SAFETY

The increasing integration of e-health into healthcare systems has resulted in a radical change in the medical care provided to the patient. eHealth was designed to increase efficiency, quality, and patient safety. According to the literature, their use is accompanied by significant challenges because the increased bureaucratic burden and the complexity of the

system contribute to the occurrence of burnout^[63,64]. Burnout associated with e-health mainly manifests itself as emotional exhaustion, cognitive overload, and decreased job satisfaction. Systematic reviews show that healthcare professionals spend valuable time, often outside of working hours, which increases stress and fatigue.

The literature shows that burnout among health professionals is not only a matter of personal well-being, but is also linked to the quality of care provided to patients, thus affecting their safety. Exhausted healthcare professionals experience reduced concentration, and limited ability to make complex decisions, which increases the risk of medical errors^[64]. Also, studies show that burnout is associated with medication errors and omissions in clinical care^[48].

At the same time, studies have highlighted the role of usability of digital systems. Doctors who report that they have greater satisfaction with using e-health have lower levels of burnout. On the contrary, doctors who do not do so well with the use of e-health are possessed with increased stress, professional dissatisfaction and possible degradation of the quality of care^[65]. In addition, the relationship between e-health, burnout, and patient safety is significantly influenced by organizational culture. Adequate staffing and appropriate provision of digital applications can mitigate the negative impact of eHealth on the well-being of healthcare professionals. In contrast, high-pressure environments with inadequate e-health support lead to burnout and increase the risk of medical errors.

In conclusion, the international literature shows that e-health can act both as a tool to enhance patient safety and as a catalyst for burnout. The adoption of human-centered digital systems, adequate training of health professionals and organizational support are key conditions for technology to contribute positively to both employee well-being and patient safety^[60].

9. FROM INDIVIDUAL DISTRESS TO SYSTEM PERFORMANCE

Burnout among health professionals, in addition to individual discomfort, directly affects health systems. Emotional exhaustion, depersonalization and reduced professional competence are gradually eroding the quality, reliability and safety of health care provision. As a result, burnout should be taken seriously by health system leaders and look for its roots in how their systems are organized, managed, and supported^[47]. The strong correlation between the well-being of healthcare staff and patient safety points out that the quality of healthcare is directly dependent on working conditions. When healthcare professionals operate under persistent pressure, excessive workload, and limited organizational support, the likelihood of medical error increases^[7].

In this regard, medical errors should be seen primarily as the results of systemic problems rather than human errors. The

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management of health systems that only emphasize responsibility and individual responsibility tend to hide their own responsibilities due to the shortcomings they have allowed to exist. In contrast, healthcare systems that invest in a culture of safety, open communication, and non-punitive error reporting are able to identify risks early and improve both staff well-being and patient safety. Supporting healthcare professionals, therefore, is not only a moral imperative but also a strategic requirement to improve system performance^[1]. On the other hand, e-health comes to provide a solution to these problems and to be a pillar of support for modern healthcare systems. Electronic health records, clinical decision support systems, and other digital interventions interact directly with daily clinical practice. Of course, special attention should be paid to their proper use otherwise we will have the opposite results. When clinical needs are aligned with digital tools, a pleasant and functional environment is created at all levels of care delivery, dramatically reducing medical errors^[29]. Improving patient safety requires a holistic approach while recognizing the interdependence between individual well-being and system performance. Burnout, medical errors, and organizational efficiency form a dynamic triangle in which weaknesses at any level can undermine the entire system^[65].

10. CONCLUSIONS

This article highlighted the multifactorial nature of burnout among healthcare professionals and its significant implications for both human resource well-being and the quality and safety of care. In the changing external environment, there is a constant increase in challenges and threats to healthcare organizations, mainly at the economic, social and technological levels, and serious environmental issues, which affect organizations in various ways.

In particular, the emergence of new needs of patients and new diseases, the aging of the population, the health behavior and lifestyle of the population, the increasing cost of health care, the increase in information, the pollution and pollution of the atmosphere and the effects of climatic conditions, affect the operation of hospitals in our country as well. They are considered risks that hospitals should be concerned about and that will probably lead them to deviate from their mission if mechanisms are not activated to take measures to deal with them.

As the external environment is constantly changing, healthcare organizations need to be flexible and adaptable to any given situation. The resulting changes may mean for organizations the need to adapt their strategy, since the changes may be crucial for their sustainability or are likely to affect the framework of their development, the organization of safe health care and the provision of quality services. Of course, for a healthcare system to be safe and truly patient-centric, it must first and foremost protect the health of its workers. The shift towards the human element and the focus on staff satisfaction is not only linked to

quality service results, but also to personal benefits for the individual himself, with his professional and personal well-being. This means that the administrations of the organizations should not only evaluate data on quality, financial performance and the number of patients, but should also evaluate various dimensions of staff well-being. Burnout is described as a syndrome of physical and emotional exhaustion, which has multiple effects on health professionals, makes it difficult to communicate with patients and degrades the quality of services provided in hospitals. By investigating, several individual interventions were recorded to deal with work stress and burnout of health professionals, without appearing to have a positive effect, in contrast to the interventions that fall under the responsibility of the management of the organizations and are related to the work environment. These interventions determine whether the individual will be efficient at work, related to medical errors, safe patient health care and the level of quality of services provided.

Creating a safer work environment is a big challenge for leadership. In particular, in order to deal with burnout, a change in working conditions is imperative. It is necessary to create conditions conducive to the development of job satisfaction, where the well-being of employees is a priority and the adoption of practices that contribute to the avoidance of conflicts and the maintenance of a climate of good cooperation in the workplace. In addition, the hospital's leadership must provide support to employees.

Subsequently, medical errors and adverse incidents all seem to be due, mainly to systems, where conditions are created in which errors evolve and swell, causing a series of situations and interactions, which favor employees to commit errors as well as not to prevent them. In most cases, they are caused by improper planning and decision-making, poor communication and lack of coordination of team members, non-compliance with procedures, limited resources, inadequate training and continuing training. In addition, the lack of information systems for identifying, recording and analyzing medical errors contributes to their concealment, resulting in no experience being gained through errors.

Medical errors, in addition to the negative consequences in terms of the quality of services provided and patient safety, complicate the already burdened operation of the health system and have a significant impact on the economy and, by extension, on society. At the same time, medical errors can have unpleasant material and moral consequences and a significant emotional impact on doctors that can last for years after the mistake is committed, so that doctors are a hidden victim and a vicious circle is created. Like the risks of medical errors, interventions to deal with them are a multifactorial issue. First of all, they should be citizen-oriented in order to understand that despite all the progress, mistakes and adverse incidents will not disappear. In addition, it should be understood that doctors and patients are jointly trying to deal with the same adversary, the

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"disease". At the same time, the medical and nursing staff must receive training in the prevention of medical errors and also must confess the mistakes and not hide them. At the same time, the detection of medical errors and adverse events needs effective reporting and recording systems. Obviously, the state, which bears a great responsibility, as many of the mistakes are due to the dysfunctions of the health system, such as understaffing, related to burnout, shortages of equipment and incentives for research, education and continuous training of health professionals, etc., must spend resources and energy in order to properly deal with the problem.

What we have learned throughout the COVID-19 pandemic, for a health system that is flexible, innovative and capable of recovering quickly in times of crisis, with effective structures, staffed with trained staff and quality integrated into the culture of staff and organizations, is the reason for a continuous effort to improve the quality of healthcare.

Particular emphasis was placed on the role of e-health, which had a dual effect. On one hand, digital health systems, such as Electronic Medical Records, Clinical Decision Support Systems, telemedicine, and Artificial Intelligence applications, have the potential to improve patient safety, reduce medical errors, and support clinical decision-making. On the other hand, when implemented without human-centered planning and adequate organizational support, they can increase the administrative and cognitive burden, contributing to the burnout of health professionals.

The conclusions of the study indicate that preventing burnout and improving patient safety require a holistic, systemic approach. Technology alone is not enough. A combination of human-centered design of digital tools, appropriate training of health professionals, strengthening of the culture of organizational safety and the adoption of policies that emphasize the well-being of human resources is required. The shift in focus from the traditional "Triple Goal" to the "Quadruple Goal," which embodies the well-being of healthcare professionals, is a crucial step in this direction. Therefore, eHealth can be a powerful tool for sustainably improving the quality and safety of care, provided that it is part of a broader strategic planning framework that recognizes the central role of healthcare professionals. Addressing burnout is not only a moral obligation for healthcare workers but also a prerequisite for providing safe, high-quality, and effective patient care.

Abbreviations: **AI:** Artificial Intelligence; **CBI:** Copenhagen Burnout Inventory; **CDSS:** Clinical Decision Support Systems; **EHR:** Electronic Health Record; **e-Health:** Electronic Health; **ICD-11:** International Classification of Diseases, 11th Revision; **MBI:** Maslach Burnout Inventory; **OLBI:** Oldenburg Burnout Inventory; **WHO:** World Health Organization

Author Contributions

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